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To The Editor-in-Chief
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- * A concise formulation of the collected information/data within the framework of the hypothesis
- * A critical evaluation of the collected information/data within the framework of the hypothesis:
- * Drawing logical and scientifically acceptable conclusions from the foregoing

The paper can take on two forms: a study investigation, or a field investigation.

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A study investigation consists of a literary study of either pure theoretical aspects and/or already published or unpublished empirical data. The conclusions and recommendations must be such that a purposeful and original contribution is made to the field of research

Field Investigation

In a field investigation the author himself collects and elaborates original data from practical situations. As a rule, it is supplemented by a literary study, once again with the inclusion of theoretical aspects and/or empirical data.

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The Role of Strategic Financial Management on Organizational Effectiveness

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Abstract

This paper attempts a comprehensive assessment of the role strategic financial managements on organizational effectiveness; it examines the implication and determinant of capital structure on the risk of corporate effectiveness in Nigeria. Findings show that debt rather than owner's equity dominate capital structure. This paper concludes that there is a need for organization to measure employee performance through a balance score card.

Introduction

Financial Management means planning, organizing, directing and controlling the financial activities such as procurement and utilization of funds of the enterprise. It means applying general management principles to financial resources of the enterprise.

1. Investment decisions includes investment in fixed assets (called as capital budgeting).

Investment in current assets are also a part of investment decisions called as working capital decisions.

2. Financial decisions - They relate to the raising of finance from various resources which will depend upon decision on type of source, period of financing, cost of financing and the returns thereby.

3. Dividend decision - The finance manager has to take decision with regards to the net profit distribution. Net profits are generally divided into two:

a. Dividend for shareholders- Dividend and the rate of it has to be decided.

b. Retained profits- Amount of retained profits has to be finalized which will depend upon expansion and diversification plans of the enterprise.

Scope and Objectives of Financial Management

The financial management is generally concerned with procurement, allocation and control of financial resources of a concern. The objectives can be-

1. To ensure regular and adequate supply of funds to the concern.

2. To ensure adequate returns to the shareholders which will depend upon the earning capacity, market price of the share, expectations of the shareholders.
3. To ensure optimum funds utilization. Once the funds are procured, they should be utilized in maximum possible way at least cost.
4. To ensure safety on investment, i.e, funds should be invested in safe ventures so that adequate rate of return can be achieved.
5. To plan a sound capital structure-There should be sound and fair composition of capital so that a balance is maintained between debt and equity capital.

Functions of Financial Management

1. **Estimation of capital requirements:** A finance manager has to make estimation with regards to capital requirements of the company. This will depend upon expected costs and profits and future programmes and policies of a concern. Estimations have to be made in an adequate manner which increases earning capacity of enterprise.
2. **Determination of capital composition:** Once the estimation have been made, the capital structure have to be decided. This involves short- term and long- term debt equity analysis. This will depend upon the proportion of equity capital a company is possessing and additional funds which have to be raised from outside parties.
3. **Choice of sources of funds:** For additional funds to be procured, a company has many choices like-
 - a. Issue of shares and debentures
 - b. Loans to be taken from banks and financial institutions
 - c. Public deposits to be drawn like in form of bonds.Choice of factor will depend on relative merits and demerits of each source and period of financing.
4. **Investment of funds:** The finance manager has to decide to allocate funds into profitable ventures so that there is safety on investment and regular returns is possible.
5. **Disposal of surplus:** The net profits decision have to be made by the finance manager. This can be done in two ways:
 - a. Dividend declaration It includes identifying the rate of dividends and other benefits
 - b. Retained profits - The volume has to be decided which will depend upon expansional, innovational, diversification plans of the company.
6. **Management of cash:** Finance manager has to make decisions with regards to cash management. Cash is required for many purposes like payment of wages and salaries, payment of electricity and water bills, payment to creditors, meeting current liabilities, maintainance of enough stock, purchase of raw materials, etc.
7. **Financial controls:** The finance manager has not only to plan, procure and utilize the funds but he also has to exercise control over finances. This can be done through many techniques like ratio analysis, financial forecasting, cost and profit control, etc. Financial activities of a firm is one of the most important and complex activities of a firm. Therefore in order to take care of these activities a financial manager performs all the requisite financial activities.

A financial manger is a person who takes care of all the important financial functions of an organization. The person in charge should maintain a far sightedness in order to ensure that the funds are utilized in the most efficient manner. His actions directly affect the Profitability, growth and goodwill of the firm.

Roles of a Financial Manager:

1. Raising of Funds

In order to meet the obligation of the business it is important to have enough cash and liquidity. A firm can raise funds by the way of equity and debt. It is the responsibility of a financial manager to decide the ratio between debt and equity. It is important to maintain a good balance between equity and debt.

2. Allocation of Funds

Once the funds are raised through different channels the next important function is to allocate the funds. The funds should be allocated in such a manner that they are optimally used. In order to allocate funds in the best possible manner the following point must be considered

- The size of the firm and its growth capability
- Status of assets whether they are long term or short tem
- Mode by which the funds are raised.

These financial decisions directly and indirectly influence other managerial activities. Hence formation of a good asset mix and proper allocation of funds is one of the most important activity.

3. Profit Planning

Profit earning is one of the prime functions of any business organization. Profit earning is important for survival and sustenance of any organization. Profit planning refers to proper usage of the profit generated by the firm. Profit arises due to many factors such as pricing, industry competition, state of the economy, mechanism of demand and supply, cost and output. A healthy mix of variable and fixed factors of production can lead to an increase in the profitability of the firm. Fixed costs are incurred by the use of fixed factors of production such as land and machinery. In order to maintain a tandem it is important to continuously value the depreciation cost of fixed cost of production. An opportunity cost must be calculated in order to replace those factors of production which has gone through wear and tear. If this is not noted then these fixed cost can cause huge fluctuations in profit.

4. Understanding Capital Markets

Shares of a company are traded on stock exchange and there is a continuous sale and purchase of securities. Hence a clear understanding of capital market is an important function of a financial manager. When securities are traded on stock market there involves a huge amount of risk involved. Therefore a financial manger understands and calculates the risk involved in this trading of shares and debentures. Its on the discretion of a financial manager as to how distribute the profits. Many investors do not like the firm to distribute the profits amongst shareholders as dividend instead invest in the business itself to enhance growth. The practices of a financial manager directly impact the operation in capital market.

The Important Roles Within a Financial Management System

An organization's financial management plays a critical role in the financial success of a business. Therefore, an organization should consider financial management a key component of the general

management of the organization. Financial management includes the tactical and strategic goals related to the financial resources of the business. Some of the specific roles included in financial management systems include accounting, bookkeeping, accounts payable and receivable, investment opportunities and risk.

Accounting and Bookkeeping

When establishing any financial management system, a business needs to determine if the management of the system will occur in-house or if it will use an outside entity. Any accounting system should measure, identify, record and communicate all of the financial information about the organization. The foundation of an effective accounting system is good bookkeeping. A bookkeeper gets the complete and accurate financial information to the accountant. While the accounting system looks at the overall financial picture of the organization, bookkeeping deals with the specific transactions that take place on a day-to-day basis.

Accounts Payables and Accounts Receivables

Account payables provide an organization with information about accounts with suppliers. This includes the outstanding sums of money owed to these suppliers. Additionally, account payables will show the cost of items purchased, how the organization made payments in the past and details about e transaction. Accounts payable will also show the work how and allow the business to approve invoices, update records and maintain an integrated document management system. Account receivables, on the other hand, records what customers owe the organization for products and services purchased. An accounts receivables system can keep track of invoices, payments, produce reminder letters for outstanding payments and calculate interest for balances owed. Additionally, accounts receivables can help the organization recover past due accounts before they become bad debts.

Investment Opportunities

Another aspect the financial management system relates to finding opportunities that can complement or benefit the organization. A business can only exploit these opportunities if the organization efficiently and effectively finds the opportunities and has the ability to pay for the desired acquisitions. By carefully considering the different aspects of the financial management system, a business can evaluate its overall financial health and determine its ability to invest in potential opportunities.

Risk

A business also must carefully evaluate risk. A primary goal of the financial management system is to minimize risks for the organization by implementing strategies that help the business to counteract unforeseen liabilities. The financial management system should include adequate insurance for property, equipment and key employees. Additionally, budgeting for quarterly and yearly working capital helps to minimize potential financial risk for the organization. Further, controlling debt and establishing a credit system with suppliers and financial institutions helps to

minimize financial risk by allowing the business operational flexibility in the event the business experiences cash flow problems.

The Role of Finance in the Strategic-Planning and Decision-Making Process

The fundamental success of a strategy depends on three critical factors: a firm's alignment with the external environment, a realistic internal view of its core competencies and sustainable competitive advantages, and careful implementation and monitoring.

Any person, corporation, or nation should know who or where they are, where they want to be, and how to get there. The strategic-planning process utilizes analytical models that provide a realistic picture of the individual, corporation, or nation at its "consciously incompetent" level, creating the necessary motivation for the development of a strategic plan. The process requires five distinct steps outlined below and the selected strategy must be sufficiently robust to enable the firm to perform activities differently from its rivals or to perform similar activities in a more efficient manner. J.A. Pearce and R.B. Robinson, (2006)

A good strategic plan includes metrics that translate the vision and mission into specific end points. C.S. Clark and S.E. Krentz (2004) This is critical because strategic planning is ultimately about resource allocation and would not be relevant if resources were unlimited. This article aims to explain how finance, financial goals, and financial performance can play a more integral role in the strategic planning and decision-making process, particularly in the implementation and monitoring stage.

Strategic planning

Strategic planning is an organization's process of defining its strategy, or direction, and making decisions on allocating its resources to pursue this strategy. It may also extend to control mechanisms for guiding the implementation of the strategy. Strategic planning became prominent in corporations during the 1960s and remains an important aspect of strategic management. It is executed by strategic planners or strategists, who involve many parties and research sources in their analysis of the organization and its relationship to the environment in which it competes.

Strategy has many definitions, but generally involves setting goals, determining actions to achieve the goals, and mobilizing resources to execute the actions. A strategy describes how the ends (goals) will be achieved by the means (resources). The senior leadership of an organization is generally tasked with determining strategy. Strategy can be planned (intended) or can be observed as a pattern of activity (emergent) as the organization adapts to its environment or competes.

Strategy includes processes of formulation and implementation; strategic planning helps coordinate both. However, strategic planning is analytical in nature (i.e., it involves "finding the dots"); strategy formation itself involves synthesis (i.e., "connecting the dots") via strategic thinking. As such, strategic planning occurs around the strategy formation activity [1]

Strategic decisions are the decisions that are concerned with whole environment in which the firm operates, the entire resources and the people who form the company and the interface between the two.

Characteristics/Features of Strategic Decisions

- a. Strategic decisions have major resource propositions for an organization. These decisions may be concerned with possessing new resources, organizing others or reallocating others.
- b. Strategic decisions deal with harmonizing organizational resource capabilities with the threats and opportunities.
- c. Strategic decisions deal with the range of organizational activities. It is all about what they want the organization to be like and to be about.
- d. Strategic decisions involve a change of major kind since an organization operates in ever-changing environment.
- e. Strategic decisions are complex in nature.
- f. Strategic decisions are at the top most level, are uncertain as they deal with the future, and involve a lot of risk.

Strategic decisions are different from administrative and operational decisions.

Administrative decisions are routine decisions which help or rather facilitate strategic decisions or operational decisions. Operational decisions are technical decisions which help execution of strategic decisions. To reduce cost is a strategic decision which is achieved through operational decision of reducing the number of employees and how we carry out these reductions will be administrative decision.

The differences between Strategic, Administrative and Operational decisions can be summarized as follows-

Strategic Decisions

Administrative Decisions

Operational Decisions

Strategic decisions are long-term decisions.

Administrative decisions are taken daily.

Operational decisions are not frequently taken.

These are considered where The future planning is concerned.

These are short-term based

Decisions.

These are medium-period based decisions.

Strategic decisions are taken in Accordance with organizational mission and vision.

These are taken according to strategic and operational

Decisions.

These are taken in accordance with strategic and administrative decision.

These are related to overall Counter planning of all Organization.

These are related to working of employees

all

Organization.

These are related to production.

These deal with organizational

Growth.

These are in welfare of employees working in an organization.

These are related to production and factory growth.

Companies employ a wide gamut of methods when assessing their performance. These methods measure everything from financial development in relation to capital structure to the relationship between labor and productivity. Organizational effectiveness and organizational efficiency constitute two such methods of performance assessment. Though sometimes confused for One another, the two measure very different things. These measurements may prove especially important to a small business operating with a limited budget and resources.

Financing Decisions and Capital Structure

Capital Structure is referred to as the ratio of different kinds of securities raised by a firm as long-term finance. The capital structure involves two decisions-

- a. Type of securities to be issued are equity shares, preference shares and long term borrowings (Debentures).
- b. Relative ratio of securities can be determined by process of capital gearing. On this basis, the companies are divided into two-
 - i. Highly geared companies - Those companies whose proportion of equity capitalization is small.
 - ii. Low geared companies - Those companies whose equity capital dominates total capitalization.

Factors Determining Capital Structure

1. **Trading on Equity-** The word "equity" denotes the ownership of the company. Trading on equity means taking advantage of equity share capital to borrowed funds on reasonable basis. It refers to additional profits that equity shareholders earn because of issuance of debentures and preference shares. It is based on the thought that if the rate of dividend on preference capital and the rate of interest on borrowed capital is lower than the general rate of company's earnings, equity shareholders are at advantage which means a company should go for a judicious blend of preference shares, equity shares as well as debentures. Trading on equity becomes more important when expectations of shareholders are high.

2. **Degree of control-** In a company, it is the directors who are so called elected representatives of equity shareholders. These members have got maximum voting rights in a concern as compared to the preference shareholders and debenture holders.

Preference shareholders have reasonably less voting rights while debenture holders have no voting rights. If the company's management policies are such that they want to retain their voting rights in their hands, the capital structure consists of debenture holders and loans rather than equity shares.

3. **Flexibility of financial plan-** In an enterprise, the capital structure should be such that there is both contractions as well as relaxation in plans. Debentures and loans can be refunded back as the time requires. While equity capital cannot be refunded at any point which provides rigidity to plans. Therefore, in order to make the capital structure possible, the company should go for issue of debentures and other loans.

4. **Choice of investors-** The company's policy generally is to have different categories of investors for securities. Therefore, a capital structure should give enough choice to all kind of investors to

invest. Bold and adventurous investors generally go for equity shares and loans and debentures are generally raised keeping into mind conscious investors.

5. Capital market condition - In the lifetime of the company, the market price of the shares has got an important influence. During the depression period, the company's capital structure generally consists of debentures and loans. While in period of boons and inflation, the company's capital should consist of share capital generally equity shares.

6. Period of financing- When company wants to raise finance for short period, it goes for loans from banks and other institutions; while for long period it goes for issue of shares and debentures.

7. Cost of financing- In a capital structure, the company has to look to the factor of cost when securities are raised. It is seen that debentures at the time of profit earning of company prove to be a cheaper source of finance as compared to equity shares where equity shareholders demand an extra share in profits.

8. Stability of sales- An established business which has a growing market and high sales turnover, the company is in position to meet fixed commitments. Interest on debentures has to be paid regardless of profit. Therefore, when sales are high, thereby the profits are high and company is in better position to meet such fixed commitments like interest on debentures and dividends on preference shares. If company is having unstable sales, then the company is not in position to meet fixed obligations. So, equity capital proves to be safe in such cases.

9. Sizes of a company- Small size business firms capital structure generally consists of loans from banks and retained profits. While on the other hand, big companies having goodwill, stability and an established profit can easily go for issuance of shares and debentures as well as loans and borrowings from financial institutions. The bigger the size, the wider is total capitalization.

Financing is limited to the optimal capital structure (debt ratio or leverage), which is the level that minimizes the firm's cost of capital. This optimal capital structure determines the firm's reserve borrowing capacity (short- and long-term) and the risk of potential financial distress. (Sidney L. Barton and Paul J. Gordon, 1987) Companies establish this structure when their cost of capital rises above that of direct competitors and there is a lack of new investments.

Profitability Ratios

This is a measure of the operational efficiency of a firm. Profitability ratios also indicate inefficient areas that require corrective actions by management; they measure profit relationships with sales, total assets, and net worth. Companies must set profitability ratio goals when they need to operate more effectively and pursue improvements in their value-chain activities.

Growth Indices

Growth indices evaluate sales and market share growth and determine the acceptable trade-off of growth with respect to reductions in cash flows, profit margins, and returns on investment. Growth usually drains cash and reserve borrowing funds, and sometimes, aggressive asset management is required to ensure sufficient cash and limited borrowing (B.T. Gale and B.Branch, 1981)

Companies must set growth index goals when growth rates have lagged behind the industry norms or when they have high operating leverage.

Risk Assessment and Management

A firm must address its key uncertainties by identifying, measuring, and controlling its existing risks in corporate governance and regulatory compliance, the likelihood of their occurrence, and their economic impact. Then, a process must be implemented to mitigate the causes and effects of those risks. (H.D. Pforsich, B.K.P. Kramer, and G.R., 2001) Companies must make these assessments when they anticipate greater uncertainty in their business or when there is a need to enhance their risk culture.

Conclusion

The introduction of the balanced scorecard emphasized an effective financial management as one of the key indicators of a firm's success and helped to link strategic goals to performance and provide timely, useful information to facilitate strategic and operational control decisions. Basically, the effectiveness of a business constitutes its ability to perform a function with optimal levels of input and output. Companies use organizational effectiveness to measure any number of things, from the relationship between employee performance and company profits to the correlation between manufacturing processes and production volume.

No set parameters exist for organizational effectiveness and it follows no definitive mathematical formula - each organization creates its own method of measuring effectiveness. Measuring effectiveness can help a small business without the ability to absorb ineffective processes modify its approach to avoid loss. This has led to the role of finance in the strategic planning process becoming more relevant than ever.

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